

Thermogravimetric Studies of Piperidine Complexes of Thiocyanates of Zinc, Cadmium, Cobalt and Nickel

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Thermal decomposition of piperidine complexes of thiocyanates of zinc, cadmium, cobalt and nickel have been studied with Stanton and Chevenard thermo balances. In every case there are two stages of loss in weight, first is due to the loss of piperidine forming $M(SCN)_n$ followed by its decomposition at higher temperature forming $M(CNS)_n$, MS and MO .

EXPERIMENTAL

Piperidine complexes viz., $Zn(CNS)_2 \cdot 2Pip$, $Cd(CNS)_2 \cdot 4Pip$, $Co(CNS)_2 \cdot 4Pip$ and $Ni(CNS)_2 \cdot 4Pip$ were freshly prepared and thermal decompositions were studied with a rate of heating maintained at 240° per hour. Thermogravimetric curves are shown in the given figure and discussed below.

FIG. 1

$Zn(CNS)_2 \cdot 2Pip$: The complex is stable upto 200° . At 200° it starts losing piperidine and the loss is complete at 350° forming $Zn(CNS)_2$, which is stable upto 390° . Above 390° zinc thiocyanate itself decomposes; the decomposition is complete at 400° and there is no change up to 500° . The residue left at this temperature is a mixture of the cyanide, sulphide and oxide of zinc.

$Cd(CNS)_2 \cdot 4Pip$: The complex is stable only up to 40°. Above 40° it slowly loses piperidine. At 70° one molecule of piperidine is lost forming $Cd(CNS)_2 \cdot 3Pip$ which is stable up to 140°. Above 140° it loses the remaining three molecules of piperidine forming $Cd(CNS)_2$ at 330°. $Cd(CNS)_2$ is stable up to 380°. At 380° cadmium thiocyanate starts decomposing and decomposition is complete at 490° and then no change in weight is observed up to 600°. The residue in this case also is a mixture of the cyanide, sulphide and oxide of cadmium.

$Co(CNS)_2 \cdot 4Pip$: The complex is stable up to 40°. Above 40° it rapidly loses piperidine forming $Co(CNS)_2$ at 360° which is stable up to 390°. At 390° cobalt thiocyanate starts decomposing and decomposition is complete at 570° and then no loss in weight is observed up to 600°. The residue in this case also is a mixture of the cyanide, sulphide and oxide of the metal.

$Ni(CNS)_2 \cdot 4Pip$: The complex is stable up to 40° above which it loses piperidine. Rate of loss of weight is very slow between 150°-180°. The pyrolysis curve is almost horizontal between 150°-180°. At 150° the composition corresponds to $Ni(CNS)_2 \cdot 1.5 Pip$. All the four molecules of piperidine are lost at 295° and nickel thiocyanate formed remains stable up to 320°. The thiocyanate starts decomposing at 320° and the decomposition is complete at 530° above which no loss in weight is observed. The residue in this case also is a mixture of cyanide, sulphide and oxide of nickel.

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